

L1 Influence on Chinese English Learners' Use of Spatial and Metaphorical Senses of the English Preposition "IN". A Learner Corpus Study
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This study explored how the accuracy of Chinese English learners' use of the preposition "IN" is influenced by their first language (L1). "IN" was selected mainly because it is highly polysemous thus posing a huge difficulty for English learners. Besides, previous studies have predominantly focused on spatial senses (e.g., Alonso et al., 2016) while metaphorical senses have not received equal attention. The focus was on both the spatial and metaphorical senses of "IN", and the potential impact of the overlap between these senses and their Chinese equivalents .

The research question the study specifically addressed is:

Does the semantic overlap between the individual senses of "IN" and its Chinese equivalent "Li" influence the accuracy of Chinese English learners' use of "IN"?

I drew data from EF-Cambridge Open Language Database (EFCAMDAT; Geertzen et al., 2013). It includes approximately 1,200,000 writings in L2 English. Most of the writings have been error-annotated, which makes it straightforward to identify errors. In the present study, I only targeted the error-annotated writings by Chinese English learners.

Since the data was highly imbalanced, I down-sampled accurate uses. Specifically, I first randomly identified 200 correct uses and 200 errors. Each correct use and error was coded in terms of "Accuracy" (Correct/Incorrect), "Sense Conveyed" based on Ferrando's (2000) taxonomy of the senses of "IN", "Sense-Type" (spatial/metaphorical), "Corresponding-Sense-Chinese" (whether the Chinese equivalent expression shares the sense conveyed) and "Corresponding-Expression-Chinese" (whether the Chinese equivalent expression can be used to express the same meaning as the original English expression).

To address the question, I modeled "accuracy" as a function of various predictors. Our models showed that L1 influence may be more prominent on the sense level than on the expression level. However, this is largely driven by the difference between spatial and metaphorical senses. When only metaphorical senses were targeted, no such association was identified.

References

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